

D5.3 Kick-Start projects report

Project title	RI-VIS
Grant Agreement No.	824063
Deliverable number	5.3
Deliverable title	Kick-Start projects report
Lead beneficiary	P3 - INFRAFRONTIER
Contributing beneficiaries	P5 - EATRIS, P6 - EMBRC-ERIC, P7 - EU-OPENSREEN
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Type	Report
Work package No.	5
Work package title	Long-term sustainability of RIs
Dissemination level	Public
Due date (in months)	36
Delivery date (actual)	31/01/2022
Description of deliverable	Summary Report of awarded projects to increase international RI visibility.

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Executive Summary

RI-VIS organised a consortium-internal call for proposals for so-called Kick-Start Projects, focused projects realisable within a six-month time-frame with an overall purpose of increasing the visibility and improving usage of research infrastructures in different world regions and ultimately to promote and facilitate cooperation.

A total of four applications were received from the RI-VIS partners EATRIS, EMBRC, EU-OPENSREEN and INFRAFRONTIER. Since all of the applications met the eligibility criteria, i.e. they suggested activities that were within the scope of the call, they teamed up European RIs and their non-European counterparts and the expected impacts were clearly laid out, the RI-VIS Steering Group decided, upon suggestion from WP5, to award all four projects.

This report describes the activities, resources used and main impacts of the four Kick-Start projects. Their outcomes clearly and successfully demonstrate that wide impact can be achieved also within quite focused and relatively short-term activities, particularly if they can build on already established links between European and international research infrastructures.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background/Introduction

Developing a common understanding of research infrastructure management and access service provision practices between the European research infrastructures and their international

counterparts is key to interoperability of services and achievement of scientific excellence, opening to the exploration of new opportunities of collaboration and a more global societal impact.

RI-VIS organised a consortium-internal call for proposals for so-called Kick-Start Projects, i.e. focused projects realisable within a six-month time-frame with an overall purpose of increasing the visibility and improving usage of research infrastructures in different world regions and ultimately to promote and facilitate cooperation.

Eligible projects could, for example, include activities to test, adopt or implement new operational systems to improve services in an international target country; activities to establish a new bilateral collaboration based on a scientific use case; or activities to identify funding/resource opportunities in Europe and the international target country and establish processes to obtain and utilise the funds to improve services to the target community.

RI-VIS awarded Kick-Start projects from four different research infrastructures, their main activities and impacts are summarised in this report.

Description of work

When it became clear that the initial action planned for increasing the mutual understanding of research infrastructure management and access service provision practices between the European research infrastructure and their international counterparts – the organisation of staff exchanges between European and non-European RIs – was not feasible to be conducted within the course of the RI-VIS project due to the COVID-19 pandemic, WP5 suggested as alternative action a call for so called Kick-Start Projects: small scale short-term projects with a potentially wide impact on trans-continental research infrastructure collaboration and visibility.

In March 2021 the following call for proposals was distributed among the RI-VIS consortium members:

Call or proposals for RI-VIS Kick-Start Awards

Applications are open for projects looking to increase visibility or/and improve usage or operation of research infrastructures (RIs) in an international context. We are looking to fund small, pilot initiatives in any area of research up to a maximum of € 10.000 per project. The projects should be completed within a period of 6 months of award.

Projects should propose new ways to further establish emerging RIs, increase the reach of existing RIs, and tackle barriers which prevent the use of available resources, particularly by (new) international communities. A positive outcome of these projects may also help the proposing RI to obtain more substantial funding from other sources or to progress towards a sustainable international partnership of RIs.

Eligible activities are for example:

- Partnering with an international RI to test, adopt or implement new operational systems to improve services in the host country;
- Partnering with an international RI to establish a new bilateral collaboration based on a scientific use case. This may include gaining access to European infrastructure by the international RI as part of the project;
- Partnering with an international RI to identify funding/resource opportunities in both Europe and the host country and to establish processes to obtain and utilise these funds to improve services to the target community in the host country.

Application procedure

Based on the conditions set out by the EC, this call will be internal to the RI-VIS consortium, i.e. the awarded Kick-Start Projects will be funded by reallocations of existing budgets within the RI-VIS project. The RI-VIS Kick-Start Awards will cover up to € 10.000.

Project proposals should contain:

- a maximum 2-page project description, indicating the required steps and actions and expected impacts.
- a project plan (Gantt chart or similar) may be helpful to identify dependencies and timelines
- a short description of the project partners (RI-VIS partner, international partner(s)) and their roles in the project.
- a breakdown of estimated costs. and their roles in the project.
- a breakdown of estimated costs.

Please send your applications to Michael Raess, the WP5.3 task lead (michael.raess@infrafrontier.eu). The call for proposals will be open until 30 April.

Please send any questions and enquiries related to the call to michael.raess@infrafrontier.eu

After the call deadline had been extended once by 14 days, a total of four applications were received from the RI-VIS partners EATRIS, EMBRC, EU-OPENSREEN and INFRAFRONTIER (summary of the received applications in Fig. 1).

Since all of the applications met the eligibility criteria, i.e. they suggested activities that were within the scope of the call, they connected European RIs and their non-European counterparts and the expected impacts were clearly laid out, the RI-VIS Executive Board decided upon suggestion from WP5 to award all four projects, but to decrease the overall amount funded per project to €7.500 to stay within the initially foreseen limit of €30.000 for this activity. All awardees accepted these conditions.

In July 2021 the following **Kick-Start Projects** started their activities:

1. EATRIS ERIC with partners from Australia, Brazil, Japan, UK, USA: **Increasing EATRIS international visibility and improving usage in Australia, Brazil, Canada, Japan, UK and USA**
2. EMBRC ERIC (Nodes from Italy, Portugal) with partners from South Africa: **Bioprospecting collaboration**
3. EU-OPENSREEN ERIC with partners from Australia: **Bilateral collaboration between Australia and Europe in the field of chemical biology and early drug discovery**
4. INFRAFRONTIER (Italian node) with partners from South Africa: **Genetic standardisation of reference mouse strains in South Africa**

RI-VIS Kick-Start Awards

	EATRIS	EMBRC	EU-Openscreen	INFRAFRONTIER
Date received	30 Apr	30 Apr	30 Apr	14 May
RI-VIS Partner	EATRIS-ERIC	EMBRC-ERIC	EU-Openscreen-ERIC	INFRAFRONTIER GmbH
European Partners		EMBRC-IT EMBRC-PT		CNR-IBBC (INFRAFRONTIER-IT)
Proposal Title	Increasing EATRIS international visibility and improving usage in Australia, Brazil, Canada, Japan, UK and USA	Bioprospecting Collaboration	Bilateral collaboration between Australia and Europe in the field of chemical biology and early drug discovery	Genetic Standardisation of Reference Mouse Strains in South Africa
International Partners	Therapeutic Innovation Australia FIOCRUZ Brasil AdMare Canada AMED Japan LifeArc UK NIH-NCATS USA	IMBM - Western Cape University South Africa	Compounds Australia at Griffith University Monash University Australia Therapeutic Innovation Australia Ltd	RAF - University of Cape Town South Africa
Project Duration	Not indicated	5 months	6 months	6 months
Direct Costs	8.000 €	10.000 €	9.800 €	9.850 €

Figure 1: Summary of awarded Kick-Start applications.

All four projects, except the one from INFRAFRONTIER, which was partially delayed due to restrictions in the context of the emergence of the COVID-19 Omicron variant (see below), were finished within the timelines indicated in the project proposals. Their main activities, resources used and achieved outputs and impacts are described below.

EATRIS Kick-Start project: Increasing EATRIS international visibility and improving usage in Australia, Brazil, Canada, Japan, UK and USA

The objective of the Kick-Start project was to support internationalisation of EATRIS activities and services. EATRIS is part of the TranslationTogether (TT) initiative, a unique collaboration of leading translational research organisations from around the world.

The Kick-Start project was designed to address barriers with respect to internationalisation of EATRIS services and activities:

- A. Lack of information on relevant services, especially training opportunities
- B. Lack of networking opportunities for the involved researchers
- C. Lack of information on funding that could support usage of resources, services and collaborative projects across continents
- D. Lack of awareness of young researchers about career and collaboration opportunities offered by Research Infrastructures such as EATRIS

The following activities were performed as part of the Kick-Start project to increase EATRIS' international visibility and improving usage in the countries involved in TT which are Australia, Brazil, Canada, Japan, UK and USA.

- A. **Initiate a webpage that will serve as a one-stop shop to find relevant training services** and to direct users to the institutions offering these training activities. Specifically, in collaboration with TT partners, information was collected on the training services offered and prepared a common structure for this information. In collaboration with a web developer, the WordPress technical backend was adapted to enable displaying of the information and curating the information in the backend to keep them up to date (<https://translationtogether.org/courses-training/>). A very important new feature is the option to filter the training services e.g. by access type or target audience. The courses were tagged using the seven characteristics of a Translational Scientist (<https://doi.org/10.1021/acsptsci.9b00022>), to maximise findability of relevant training services. In addition, a simplified visual of the seven characteristics was produced in order to make it suitable for integration in websites and videos.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the training services database added to the TT website.

- B. Initiate a series of virtual workshops** to offer scientists the opportunity to explore collaboration opportunities for which complementary resources and services will be needed. Building on a successful pilot event that was attended by 65 participants and positively evaluated by participants, all TT partners started recruitment of projects to be featured using a variety of channels including newsletters, mailing campaigns and direct communication. Across all TT partners, there was an extremely limited response rate. The analysis highlighted that the challenge could be attributed to two factors: The first factor was that the series was planned as a bridge across diseases, technical platforms and scientific disciplines to reach a diverse and complementary audience. However, this proved to hinder targeted communication. It was therefore decided to adapt the approach and do a workshop targeted to a defined topic. On 15/12/2021 a workshop on Gene Therapy took place with high profile attendance across TT partners. The second factor was the lack of potential funding. Follow-up workshops will therefore be planned based on outcome of the funding scan (see Kick-Start activity C).
- C. Identify dedicated funding opportunities** that will support access to services and resources from Brazil, Japan, Canada, US, Australia and UK. In collaboration with the consultant, EATRIS refined the criteria that funding opportunities need to meet to enable use of EATRIS services, access to the different partners. It was agreed to search for Foundations, Philanthropy organisations and Funding organisations that would support international cooperation in the areas key of TT. The funding scan revealed 32 organisations that would allow for international collaboration of TT partners and provides a great source for internationalisation of EATRIS' activities and services.

Name funding organization	Fit for Transition Together (Y/N)	Activities that can be funded	Field of research / indication	Foundation based in (Country)	TT countries	Specific call	International collaboration (Y/N)	Information about collaboration / call	Information about organization	Link to website
Action Medical Research	N	N/A	N/A	UK	UK	Project grant and Fellowship award	N	Only open to UK applicants	The aim of the charity is to prevent and treat disease and disability by funding vital medical research in hospitals or research institutions across the UK. The remit focuses on child health to include problems affecting pregnancy, children, babies, children and young people. Within child health, the charity supports a broad spectrum of research with the objective of preventing and treating disease and disability.	Link
Alzheimer's Drug Discovery Foundation (ADDF)	Y	Collaborative Research, Advances & Awareness	Neurodegenerative & Neurological Disorders	US	All	There are different core programmes and additional joint funding opportunities	Y	May depend on the specific call. But no mention of where the partners should be based.	The emphasis is on clinical research or research at the interface between clinical and basic science. The ADDF provides funding to academic centres and biotech firms around the world that are advancing therapeutic and biomarker development for Alzheimer's and related dementias. Funding will go towards several key areas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Translational research to develop new drugs and build preclinical evidence. IND-enabling studies and early-stage clinical trials for novel and repurposed drugs. Development and validation of plasma, CSF, neuroimaging and digital biomarkers. Epidemiological studies and comparative effectiveness research. 	Link
Alzheimer's Research UK	Y	Collaborative Research	Neurodegenerative & Neurological Disorders	UK	All	Different call for proposals offered each year. They offer the Major Project or Dementia Consortium.	Y	For the Major Project call, the lead applicant must be based in a UK research institution, and the application can include researchers or institutions outside the UK. For the Dementia Consortium, applications are acceptable from applicants based at established research institutions worldwide.	Alzheimer's Research UK is the leading dementia and Alzheimer's disease research charity. They have built a reputation as a flexible and responsive funder, committed to supporting the best and most innovative research from across the field. They encourage applicants that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> address fundamental gaps in our knowledge of disease processes; have a translational path or vision; are collaborative and transparent; ensure reports and data are shared with the scientific community. 	Link
Alzheimer's Society	N	N/A	Neurodegenerative & Neurological Disorders	UK	UK	Offer different calls over the year	N	Only open to UK applicants	Alzheimer's Society aims to understand the underlying causes of the condition, improve diagnosis and care, identify ways to prevent dementia and searching for a cure. The Society invests £20 million a year into dementia research, by funding a variety of dementia research projects and initiatives across the UK. As the nation's largest private, not-for-profit source of funds for scientists studying cancer, the American Cancer Society remains committed to funding basic, translational, clinical, and cancer control research. By funding scientific research, the American Heart Association (AHA) supports those fighting cardiovascular disease, including heart disease and stroke.	Link
American Cancer Society	N	N/A	Oncology, Translational Research	US	US	Multiple calls available per year	N	Only funding available for US investigators	Funding research is a cornerstone of the AHA's lifesaving mission. The AHA is the largest not-for-profit funding source for cardiovascular and cerebrovascular disease research next to the federal government. New knowledge resulting from AHA funding benefits millions of lives in every corner of the U.S. and around the world: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transition into medical advancements; Updated guidelines for healthcare providers to most effectively treat patients and improve people's well-being; Builds careers in science and research. 	Link
American Heart Association (AHA)	N	Collaborative Research	Cardiovascular & Hematological Disorders	US	US	Multiple programmes open during the year, such as the Collaborative Sciences Award	N	This award fosters innovative collaborative approaches to research projects that promote novel pairing of investigators from at least two broadly disparate disciplines. However, grantees must be US citizens, and awards for research to be performed outside the United States are limited to Principal Investigators who are United States citizens.	ADCF's mission is to back brilliant research by giving scientists the technology and equipment they need to find new and improved ways to prevent, detect and treat ALL types of cancer. ADCF has a commitment to achieving the best possible clinical outcomes through high quality basic and translational research. Grant applications in support of this general philosophy are encouraged. Collecting, sharing, analyzing and interpreting health-related data are essential to the planning, implementation, and evaluation of public health practice as well as enabling advanced knowledge for health-emergencies preparedness. The desired outcome of this call is development of tools and protocols that are "open source" to facilitate collaboration among researchers in UK. This effort is focused on filling data science gaps and challenges whose solutions will address global health problems while fostering multidisciplinary collaborations among researchers. The British Heart Foundation funds over £200 million of research each year into all heart and circulatory diseases and the things that cause them (heart disease, stroke, vascular dementia, Diabetes). Translational Awards aim to progress the development of novel, innovative technologies towards benefits to human cardiovascular health. The scheme supports the development of technologies with	Link
Australian Cancer Research Foundation (ACRF)	N	N/A	Translational Research, Oncology	Australia	Australia	Annual Research Grant	N	The grant supports research by groups and institutions with outstanding credentials and/or expertise in cancer research, to facilitate new and sustainable programs and to provide platforms that will lead to Australia's cancer research capacity. There is no mention about international collaborations.	ADCF's mission is to back brilliant research by giving scientists the technology and equipment they need to find new and improved ways to prevent, detect and treat ALL types of cancer. ADCF has a commitment to achieving the best possible clinical outcomes through high quality basic and translational research. Grant applications in support of this general philosophy are encouraged. Collecting, sharing, analyzing and interpreting health-related data are essential to the planning, implementation, and evaluation of public health practice as well as enabling advanced knowledge for health-emergencies preparedness. The desired outcome of this call is development of tools and protocols that are "open source" to facilitate collaboration among researchers in UK. This effort is focused on filling data science gaps and challenges whose solutions will address global health problems while fostering multidisciplinary collaborations among researchers. The British Heart Foundation funds over £200 million of research each year into all heart and circulatory diseases and the things that cause them (heart disease, stroke, vascular dementia, Diabetes). Translational Awards aim to progress the development of novel, innovative technologies towards benefits to human cardiovascular health. The scheme supports the development of technologies with	Link
Bill & Melinda Gates	Y	Resources & Tools for Investigators, Collaborative Research	M Health, AI, Medical Software / Apps	US	Brazil	Strengthening Data Science Capacity and the Ecosystem, Ending Zero-Costs for Public Health Interventions	Y	Africa, India, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Nepal, and Brazil	ADCF's mission is to back brilliant research by giving scientists the technology and equipment they need to find new and improved ways to prevent, detect and treat ALL types of cancer. ADCF has a commitment to achieving the best possible clinical outcomes through high quality basic and translational research. Grant applications in support of this general philosophy are encouraged. Collecting, sharing, analyzing and interpreting health-related data are essential to the planning, implementation, and evaluation of public health practice as well as enabling advanced knowledge for health-emergencies preparedness. The desired outcome of this call is development of tools and protocols that are "open source" to facilitate collaboration among researchers in UK. This effort is focused on filling data science gaps and challenges whose solutions will address global health problems while fostering multidisciplinary collaborations among researchers. The British Heart Foundation funds over £200 million of research each year into all heart and circulatory diseases and the things that cause them (heart disease, stroke, vascular dementia, Diabetes). Translational Awards aim to progress the development of novel, innovative technologies towards benefits to human cardiovascular health. The scheme supports the development of technologies with	Link
British Heart Foundation	N	N/A	Cardiovascular & Hematological Disorders, Translational Research	UK	UK	Different call for proposals offered each year. They offer a Translational	N	Main applicant must be based in the UK.	ADCF's mission is to back brilliant research by giving scientists the technology and equipment they need to find new and improved ways to prevent, detect and treat ALL types of cancer. ADCF has a commitment to achieving the best possible clinical outcomes through high quality basic and translational research. Grant applications in support of this general philosophy are encouraged. Collecting, sharing, analyzing and interpreting health-related data are essential to the planning, implementation, and evaluation of public health practice as well as enabling advanced knowledge for health-emergencies preparedness. The desired outcome of this call is development of tools and protocols that are "open source" to facilitate collaboration among researchers in UK. This effort is focused on filling data science gaps and challenges whose solutions will address global health problems while fostering multidisciplinary collaborations among researchers. The British Heart Foundation funds over £200 million of research each year into all heart and circulatory diseases and the things that cause them (heart disease, stroke, vascular dementia, Diabetes). Translational Awards aim to progress the development of novel, innovative technologies towards benefits to human cardiovascular health. The scheme supports the development of technologies with	Link

Figure 3: Screenshot of the funding opportunities report delivered by the consultancy company.

D. Lack of awareness of young researchers about career and collaboration opportunities offered by Research Infrastructures such as EATRIS. In May 2021, before the start of the Kick-Start project, EATRIS presented to young researchers during the ENABLE conference (www.enablenetwork.eu) the career and collaboration opportunities in Research Infrastructures. While the young researchers were interested in the opportunity, feedback was that more tangible examples showcasing these opportunities would be needed. Therefore, EATRIS produced a series of videos that can be shared via social media platforms such as YouTube, showcasing the career and collaboration opportunities offered by TT. A set of guiding questions was developed, and suitable presenters identified. These were selected to achieve a good balance of different career stages, job profiles, countries and gender. The videos were equipped with intro and outro slides by a video editor.

Figure 4: Screenshot of video created.

Impact

The website and video produced during the Kick-Start project, enabled EATRIS to increase the visibility of its services to an international audience. The funding scan and workshop series have laid a very strong foundation for the future use of EATRIS services by the international TT partners.

Resources used

Category	Description	Costs
Other direct costs	Database plugin for TranslationTogether website	1,720€
Other direct costs	Consultancy to identify funding that enables the TT partners to access EATRIS services & resources	4,500€
Other direct costs	Video editing (100 minutes footage)	1,320€
Other direct costs	Visual design	2,000€
Personnel costs		0 €
Total		9,600€

EMBRC Kick-Start project: Bioprospecting Collaboration

Background

Marine biodiversity is recognised as a source of particular interest for identifying novel compounds, bioactive substances, medical treatments, and biotechnologies. EMBRC has as one of its priorities the supply and access to European marine biodiversity and through a dispersed platform of infrastructures and scientific expertise gives all European scientists a gateway to unlock their value. Consequently, bioprospecting is a strategically important activity for EMBRC, tying into the blue bioeconomy strategy and Europe's Green Deal, as well as to its operators.

The uniqueness of EMBRC does not come from the instrumentation and technical capacities in themselves. It is quite clear that across science the use of equipment and methods is common. The uniqueness of the pipelines in EMBRC is the organisms that are being studied (isolated from the environment or existing as an isolate in a collection) in the countries and institutions that are affiliated to EMBRC and the custom designed and built platforms and pipelines to investigate these rich resources.

The Institute for Microbial Biotechnology and Metagenomics (IMBM) (<http://imbm.co.za/>) was established in 2007 and is based within the Department of Biotechnology at the University of the Western Cape (UWC), Bellville, South Africa. The Institute's Research and Innovation (R&I) programme focuses on the use of (meta)genomics for the development of technologies to produce novel, high-value natural products for the pharmaceutical, cosmeceutical, food & beverage and agricultural industries, as well as products for industrial applications.

IMBM contacted EMBRC in October 2020, enquiring about the availability of expertise and infrastructure in EMBRC for the isolation and characterisation of bioactive(s) of interest to the IMBM R&I programme. The IMBM would greatly benefit from access to screening platforms, particularly antifungal and antibacterial activity, which would speed up its biodiscovery programme. It was decided to use the RI-VIS Kick-Start programme to allow IMBM to test EMBRC's capabilities, and for EMBRC to test its ability to support bioprospecting in a punctual and timely manner.

Work Plan & Activities

Based on the needs of IMBM, EMBRC Portugal (EMBRC-PT) and EMBRC Italy (EMBRC-IT) were selected to support the project, providing purification and structural characterisation and bioactive screening respectively. The project was conceived to fulfil the objectives of EMBRC in relation to a) creating interoperability between nodes with different elements of bioprospecting, b) establishing standard operating procedures for sample receipt and storage as well as identifying and overcoming pitfalls linked to transport of biological material between continents and issues linked to biological material transfer agreements as well as c) demonstrating and testing the performance of EMBRC bioprospecting pipelines.

Figure 5: General snapshot of the interaction foreseen in the context of the RI-VIS Kick-Start award between EMBRC and IMBM, South Africa. An iterative process occurred between partners and close communication occurred between IMBM and the nodes of EMBRC involved in the screening to maximise the project progress and by establishing decision points during project development corrective measures or interventions were rapid.

All biological materials were provided by IMBM to EMBRC. The proposed project was on the isolation and characterisation of specific bioactives from two priority samples from IMBM. Unfortunately, problems arising in the production of biomass containing lantipeptides meant that it was not possible to proceed with the bioactivity screening initially foreseen for these compounds in EMBRC Italy (EMBRC-IT). The second objective was purification and structural characterisation of a lichenysin from a crude extract provided by the IMBM to EMBRC-Portugal (PT) and depending on dereplication outcomes screening of bioactivity in EMBRC-IT.

Results

EMBRC-PT successfully characterised the chemical structure of a diversity of lichenysin-related molecules.

The first challenge of the project was to establish a biological material transfer agreement (BMTA). The experience of Dr Anita Burger, the IMBM Research and Innovation Manager facilitated this process as she brought her vast experience and the established track record of IMBM in this arena and also shipping logistics to the project. This allowed the BMTA to be rapidly drafted and signed (in 3-4 weeks) allowing almost immediate initiation of the project. The second challenge was also overcome by Dr Anita Burger and the team in IMBM and in discussion with EMBRC.PT (CCMAR), sample transportation conditions were agreed, logistics of transfer rapidly dealt with, and biological samples were dispatched to EMBRC.PT. Due to the combined efforts of IMBM and CCMAR the samples were not held up in customs and after cursory detainment they were rapidly released and arrived in CCMAR (EMBRC.PT) in pristine condition.

The chemistry platform led by Dr José Paulo Silva led the project. Before any analysis was initiated a conference call was held to discuss the objectives and the foreground knowledge held about the compounds by IMBM identifying at this stage potential pitfall or issue with the samples.

Documentation was exchanged and due to the short timeline and the urgency of the project, essential reagents, standards, and materials were purchased immediately for the analysis.

Figure 6: The timeline and main steps of the project development.

The project was immediately started with preliminary steps being taken to optimise the extraction approaches, and then optimisation of the LC-MS analysis followed.

LC-MS Profiles

Figure 7: A typical LC-MS profile obtained for the bacterial biomass from IMBM.

The smooth flow of the project was due to the close communication and interaction between the team members in IMBM (Lonnie van Zyl) and CCMAR (José Paulo Silva) that led to a real time exchange of results and opinions and this accelerated the project since it was catalysed by the pre-existing knowledge and expertise of the team in IMBM and the dialogue with the chemists in CCMAR.

Detailed results are not shown as they are under a confidentiality agreement. It should be noted that after extensive analysis it was concluded that the compounds isolated did not present uniqueness and so it was decided not to proceed with bioactivity screening. Instead, a further extract was analysed for promising leads for future screening targets.

Table of Service Costs

Code	Description	Quantity	Unit Price (€)	Sub-Total (€)
S-TEC	Structural chemistry of microbial samples provided by the Institute for Microbiological Biotechnology and Metagenomics, University of Western Cape, South Africa	1	10.000,00	10.000,00
			Sub-Total (€)	10.000,00
			*VAT	-
			Total (€)	10.000,00

*Vat not included

Obs. R & D Specialized service to be provided by CEIB Group and Chemistry Platform
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Tangible outcomes

The Kick-Start programme was a great opportunity to engage with an institution interested in working with us and using EMBRC services to compliment their own. In terms of the work planned in the project, the following tangible outcomes were identified:

- RI-VIS Kick-Start improved the visibility of EMBRC bioprospecting facilities and created new partnerships;
- Established simple biological material transfer agreements, contract conditions, communication channels and the shipping logistics;
- Interoperability of two EMBRC nodes was improved as was communication with headquarters through project planning and meetings;
- Weaknesses and problem areas were identified for improvement;
- High quality biomass and strong consultation meant high quality results were obtained and new opportunities for the future identified.

Impact & Future Plans

EMBRC and IMBM were successful in mounting a fruitful collaboration, with the participating partners highlighting the excellent communication between the partners, the constructive and informative discussions, and the high quality of the results and outputs. Further collaborations are being pursued along three axes: 1) timely service provision; 2) funded collaborative bioprospecting projects; 3) establishing long-term partnership to explore novel products from the sea. In terms of service provision, IMBM will complement its services in bioprospecting with the bioactive screening and chemical structure elucidation offered by EMBRC. Funding opportunities have been identified and a project is planned for submission in September to the Eurostars call. Finally, an invitation has been extended to IMBM for a visit to EMBRC early summer to explore opportunities for deeper partnership between the two organisations.

EU-OPENSSCREEN Kick-Start project: Bilateral collaboration between Australia and Europe in the field of chemical biology and early drug discovery

Introduction

EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC is the European RI for chemical biology and early drug discovery. By screening large collections of compounds, novel chemical probes and novel drug leads are identified. This drug discovery approach, however, requires access to a bespoke infrastructure of high-throughput compound screening platforms, comprehensive and chemically diverse screening compound collections, automated compound management capabilities and hit-to-lead optimisation chemistry expertise. EU-OPENSSCREEN aims to democratise access to such a critical infrastructure for researchers worldwide to support drug discovery efforts in academic and industry.

An important aspect in drug discovery is the quality of the screening compound collection. While the majority of academic compound collections predominantly consist of commercial compounds, compounds synthesised by academic chemists and natural products represent a rich, untapped source for novel chemical diversity. With the aim to make these invaluable resources accessible to a broader scientific community, EU-OPENSSCREEN provides chemists with the opportunity to make their compounds available, in a regulated and transparent framework, to biologists, who test these compounds in suitable bioassays. Chemists can thereby expose their compounds to a broad range of different biological targets and screen for unknown bioactivities of their compounds, which would otherwise not be feasible via bilateral collaborations with individual scientists. After a compound is identified as an active 'hit' compound, the chemist (who submitted the compound) and the biologist (who developed the bioassay) initiate a research collaboration to progress the compound further.

The storage, curation and distribution as well as the screening of these collections require a dedicated infrastructure. In Europe and Australia, EU-OPENSSCREEN and Griffith University's Compounds Australia (CA), located at the Griffith Institute for Drug Discovery (GRIDD) in Brisbane, have been established to provide access to such critical infrastructure and expertise. Together with Therapeutic Innovation Australia (TIA), a not-for-profit research infrastructure organisation that supports Australian Government Initiatives, the three parties signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) in 2014.

Figure 8: Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) Signature Ceremony at the Australian Embassy in Brussels, May 17, 2014. (Photo: Bahne Stechmann, EU-OPENSREEN).

Objective

Building on this tripartite agreement, a 6-month pilot project was proposed between several Australian (Griffith University, Therapeutic Innovation Australia and Monash University) and European partners (EU-OPENSREEN) to establish a bilateral collaboration around the exchange chemical compounds and bioactivity data.

Project partners:

EU-OPENSREEN ERIC (www.eu-openscreen.eu) is the European Research Infrastructure for Chemical Biology and brings together chemical biology networks and partner institutions for high-throughput screening and medicinal chemistry across eight European countries. The international not-for-profit EU-OPENSREEN ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) was founded in April 2018, with Germany as the host country, and is jointly funded by eight countries on a long-term basis. EU-OPENSREEN operates the open-access European Chemical Biology Database (ECBD, <https://ecbd.eu/>) and a central compound management facility which manages, curates and distributes EU-OPENSREEN's compound collections, incl. a diversity collection of ca. 100,000 compounds, a collection with ca. 2,500 known bioactives, a fragment library and a growing collection of compounds that are being submitted by chemists. Contact person: Bahne Stechmann

Compounds Australia at Griffith University: GRIDD's Compounds Australia (<https://www.griffith.edu.au/griffith-sciences/compounds-australia>) is Australia's only dedicated compound management facility and securely stores and curates sample libraries submitted by Australian-based chemists. Compounds Australia provides access to critical infrastructure and expertise to ensure flexible, efficient, reproducible and cost-effective compound management, supporting biological characterisation of compounds throughout the drug discovery pipeline. It manages a national 'Open' compound collection, and numerous 'Closed' or proprietary compound

collections and provides these sample collections to academic, not-for-profit and industry researchers. The guiding principles of Compounds Australia are to enable new collaborations between chemists and biologists and to add value to the already excellent synthetic, organic and natural product chemistry in the Australasian region. Contact person: Moana Simpson, Wilma James

Griffith University: Natural products have been the single most productive source of leads for the development of drugs. In the area of cancer, over the time frame from 1981 to date, 64.9% of approved drugs and drug candidates are of natural origin. The Griffith Institute for Drug Discovery (GRIDD, <https://www.griffith.edu.au/institute-drug-discovery>) at Griffith University has a long history and formidable reputation in natural product drug discovery research. Led by A/Prof Yun Feng, GRIDD chemists are leveraging this expertise through the establishment of a GRIDD Natural Product Derived Compounds Set comprising 500 pure compounds (<https://www.griffith.edu.au/institute-drug-discovery/unique-resources/naturebank>). This is a unique compound collection in that compounds: (i) are pure natural products from rich Australian Flora and Fauna; (ii) possess diverse structural features that cover a vast chemical space and; (iii) have drug like physicochemical properties that comply with Lipinski's rules. The GRIDD Pure Natural Product Compounds Set are deposited at Compounds Australia, part of the NCRIS-funded Therapeutic Innovation Australia network. The compound set is to provide to academic, not-for-profit and industry researchers, enabling new collaborations and value adding to other publicly accessible compounds in the Compounds Australia collection. Contact person: Assoc Professor Yun Feng

Monash University: The Australian Translational Medicinal Chemistry Facility (ATMCF, <https://www.monash.edu/atmcf>) is hosted by the Monash Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, and with Director Professor Jonathan Baell, embodies considerable experience in recognition of pan-assay interference compounds (PAINS), implementing best design of quality HTS libraries and recognition of quality screening compounds, best hit triage practices and planning of efficient SAR strategies. The ATMCF has its own compound registration system and storage of stock for all proprietary compounds, a cheminformatics suite and all the equipment required for full QC of samples of interest. Contact person: Professor Jonathan Baell

Therapeutic Innovation Australia Ltd (TIA): Therapeutic Innovation Australia (TIA, <https://www.therapeuticinnovation.com.au/>) is the lead agent for the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy "Therapeutic Innovation Australia" project funded by the Australian Department of Education, Skills and Employment. To enhance the progression of early-stage discoveries through to preclinical development, TIA has formed a Small Molecules Capability which is an integrated capability network of five National Research Infrastructure (NRI) across Australia, including Compounds Australia and ATMCF. This group of NRI caters to the needs of researchers and SMEs in search of expertise to progress small molecules, from accessing a unique compound and hit identification at one end of the drug discovery pipeline to a drug candidate being progressed into an IND- or CTN-enabling toxicology program at the other. To further support researchers and SMEs, TIA has established Pipeline Accelerator, a voucher-based access scheme. This scheme is intended to reduce the cost of access to capability within TIA Consortium, including a network of high throughput screening centres. Contact person: Stuart Newman, MJ Chua

Description of work

Exchanging physical samples between Australia and Europe requires an agreement from all parties on several issues: Ownership of the results and intellectual property; data publication policies, including requirements to disclose structural data of compounds and/or primary screening/bioactivity data; selection of compounds (e.g. selection criteria, minimum amounts); procedure to physically exchange samples; access to samples by third parties; operational and data standardisation; and others. Due to COVID-19 related travel restrictions, the discussions between the project partners took place during virtual meetings and by email correspondence.

The discussions during the pilot project revolved predominantly around compounds from Australia to be integrated into the EU-OPENSSCREEN academic screening collection. As a research infrastructure, EU-OPENSSCREEN offers chemists to make their compounds available to other biologists, who test these compounds in suitable bioassays at one of the EU-OPENSSCREEN partner sites. Chemists can thereby test the effect of their compounds against a variety of biological targets to uncover novel bioactivities of their compounds, which would otherwise be difficult to realise via multiple bilateral collaborations with individual researchers. EU-OPENSSCREEN requires the submitting chemists to disclose the compound structures, the deposition of the primary screening data in the European Chemical Biology Database after an optional embargo period of up to three years (to safeguard IPR of researchers), as well as a minimum amount of 5-10 mg of compounds that must be >90% pure.

A Material Transfer Agreement (MTA) for compound submissions is available, which defines the terms and conditions along these pre-defined guidelines. After the initial virtual project meeting, where the compound submission procedure and criteria were presented, the MTA was shared with the Australian project partners.

Chemists need to make at least 5-10mg of their compounds available, if they wish to submit compounds to EU-OPENSSCREEN. The material is centrally stored in EU-OPENSSCREEN's Central Compound Management Facility (CCMF) in Berlin, quality-controlled by LC-MS (Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry), re-formatted, 'profiled' (<https://www.eu-openscreen.eu/services/bioproteotyping-assays.html>) and smaller aliquots are then shipped to EU-OPENSSCREEN's partner sites. The isolation and characterisation of natural compounds derived from e.g., plants, fungi or marine invertebrates is a laborious, time-consuming process starting from crude extracts, to pre-fractionated extracts and finally the purified natural products with known structures. Well-characterised, pure natural compounds are thus precious material and available only in small quantities. The project partners therefore focused the discussions on synthetic compounds.

The mandate to disclose the compound structure is central to the concept of EU-OPENSSCREEN, which is one of the few chemical biology/drug discovery initiatives that makes 'negative' bioactivity data (i.e. information that one compound is not active against one biological target at a given concentration) publicly available. The structural information of compounds represents sensitive data, and the requirement to disclose this type of information entails that the chemist selects the compounds very carefully before making them available. In the context of this pilot project, the project partners agreed to focus on compounds with already published/known structures.

Different options for the exchange of the physical samples have been considered. Compounds Australia operates a state-of-the-art compound management infrastructure to make compounds

available at low cost in flexible screening and assay-ready formats to academic and not-for-profit researchers. The samples have been solubilised and stored in DMSO at 5mM and have been reformatted into a microplate library for ease of providing assay-ready multi-formatted plates. One option, which has been discussed during this pilot project, is that Compounds Australia provides compounds in solution directly to EU-OPENSSCREEN's screening partner sites in small quantities. Alternatively, compounds are provided in dry powders and transferred to EU-OPENSSCREEN's CCMF, and processed as described above. The latter option represents the standard procedure for the EU-OPENSSCREEN's compound submission model and is therefore strongly favoured by EU-OPENSSCREEN. The discussions will focus on this model.

EU-OPENSSCREEN recently acquired a fragment library of approximately 1,000 fragments, derived from the fragment space of the EU-OPENSSCREEN screening library with 100,000 compounds. In Australia, the Monash Fragment Platform provides academic and commercial researchers with access to fragment-based drug discovery (FBDD) technologies for their therapeutic targets, and uses its own high-quality, in-house fragment library which is curated by Compounds Australia. Compounds Australia also maintains a small fragment library made available through the University of Adelaide. In order to assess the similarity of these fragment libraries, the structural information of the structural data files of EU-OPENSSCREEN's fragment library has been shared with the project partners.

Conclusions:

After the signature of the Memorandum of Understanding between the Griffith University, Compounds Australia, TIA, and EU-OPENSSCREEN in 2014, the project partners from Australia and Europe resumed discussions about the exchange chemical compounds and bioactivity data. This RI-VIS Kick-Start project provided a suitable framework for these discussions to take place during an ambitious timeframe of only six months. Several important, complex issues have been discussed in detail. Though no compounds have been exchanged yet, the discussions arrived at an advanced stage and will be continued after the lifetime of this pilot project (and of the RI-VIS project) with the aim to exchange samples in 2022.

INFRAFRONTIER RI-VIS Kick-Start project: Genetic Standardisation of Reference Mouse Strains in South Africa

Contact: Dr. Asrar Ali Khan (asrar.khan@infrafrontier.eu)

International Partners:

UCT-RAF: The University of Cape Town (UCT) Research Animal Facility (RAF)

CNR-IBBC: The National Research Council - The Institute of Biochemistry and Cell Biology

Background

Biomedical research in South Africa and Africa depends to a large extent on the use of wildtype and genetically-altered rodents. However, the maintenance of the high genetic quality of rodent colonies in many (South) African institutions has been impeded by the large physical distance between the institutions and the sole reliance on international commercial suppliers of rodent lines. This translates to a prohibitively high cost for the international transport of animals, preventing the import of founder genetics to revive the genetic quality of African lines. The result is significant genetic drift over multiple decades, with largely uncontrolled and deteriorating genetic quality of research rodents in many South African and African institutions. The UCT-RAF is uniquely positioned to assist in addressing this challenge, by importing and archiving cryopreserved rodent embryos of known genetic quality, rederiving the animals in South Africa, and distributing the strains to South African and potentially other African institutions. Other prominent research institutes like the South African PreClinical Drug Development Platform (PCDDP) have requested UCT-RAF to quality-control wildtype strains, as no other rodent embryology laboratories have the required capabilities, and it is cost-prohibitive to establish new facilities. The UCT-RAF is an active member of the South African Association for Laboratory Animal Science (SAALAS) and the Pan-African Network for Laboratory Animal Science and Ethics (PAN-LASE), with the distribution of rederived animals being enabled via these networks.

For the RI-VIS Kick-Start project it was thus proposed to import cryopreserved embryos for the most commonly used wildtype lines to the UCT-RAF for rederivation. Rederived lines were to initially be subjected to genetic QC testing at the UCT-RAF, prior to distribution of animals to other institutions. To ensure high impact and sustainability, sufficient numbers of embryos were to be supplied in order to enable three (3) sequential cycles of rederivation every 3.5 to 5 years or after ten generations for a period of 10-15 years. The embryos were to be provided by CNR-IBBC Monterotondo, the Italian INFRAFRONTIER-EMMA node. In short, given the UCT-RAF's rodent reproduction biotechnology laboratory (since 2013), and experienced embryo technologist (trained by Jackson laboratories and INFRAFRONTIER-EMMA group at CNR-IBBC Monterotondo), this project could significantly improve the quality and reproducibility of biomedical research involving mouse models across the sub-continent.

Summary of Activities

Provided by Kerith Coulson, UCT-RAF

On 5 July 2021, it was confirmed that the INFRAFRONTIER submission to the RI-VIS Kick-Start project had been accepted and the proposed project could go ahead as planned. The timeline for cryopreserving embryos was discussed between UCT-RAF and CNR-IBBC who would be responsible for cryopreserving approximately 250 embryos per strain for 6 individual mouse strains. Owing to the known poor performance of the 129/sv strain and the schedule of the CNR-IBBC cryopreservation laboratory, only 52 embryos had been cryopreserved for this strain by 3 September. By the third week of September, five of the six strains (see table) had been completely cryopreserved and in lieu of the short time period available to complete the project, a decision was taken to send the shipment to South Africa without completing the 129/SV cryopreservation (only anticipated in November).

Strain	Number of embryos	Number of straws	Cryopreservation complete?
C57BL/6J	250	10	Yes
C57BL/6NTac	250	10	Yes
BALB/cByJ	150	10	Yes
129SvlmJ	50	2	No
CD1	250	10	Yes
NU:NU	250	10	Yes

The application process to apply for a veterinary import permit was sent on 16 September and the permit was approved on 6 October (valid for 3 months). At the time South Africa was just coming out of a prolonged wave of COVID-19 infections with the Delta variant – prolific between June and August 2021 which resulted in many countries banning any travel or international flights to South Africa.

In October 2021, UCT-RAF and CNR-IBBC began approaching courier services but unfortunately incurred some indecisions regarding which institution (UCT-RAF, CNR-IBBC or INFRAFRONTIER) would be liable for the costs. After realising that INFRAFRONTIER was not in an ideal position to pay certain service providers as they did not have a customer account with these couriers, it was decided and confirmed by Dr Marcello Raspa on 17 November that all invoices could be directed to CNR-IBBC with invoices supplied to INFRAFRONTIER by the end of December 2021 for reimbursement through the Kick-Start grant.

CNR-IBBC again contacted couriers for quotes and soon discovered that there was a lack of dedicated flights out of Europe and that several countries worldwide were listed in an “emergency status” and thus transport of any kind was stopped due to the COVID-19 pandemic. On 26 November a new variant of the COVID-19 (Omicron) was discovered in South Africa which sparked a new series of border closures and travel bans to the country. This was communicated to the CNR-IBBC team and an urgency to ship the cryopreserved samples was conveyed. Unfortunately, the

CNR-IBBC team was struggling to contact the relevant authorities in South Africa which severely affected the import progress.

By 1 December, only one quote could be supplied to INFRAFRONTIER, that of the SNP panels to test the genetic integrity of the 6 strains. All other costs were subject to travel restrictions and thus could not be supplied in advance since none of the shipping between countries had yet occurred.

In anticipation of the soon to expire veterinary import permit into South Africa, a second permit was applied for on 13 December. Communication between CNR-IBBC and UCT-RAF revealed that the courier chosen by CNR-IBBC was still struggling with obtaining the correct information to ship the cryopreserved embryos. After a short discussion it was decided to change couriers in the hope of accomplishing the shipment before the end of January 2022. The second veterinary import permit was received on 21 January 2022.

Overview of Resources

- Costs for Mouse 384 SNP Panel: €2.188,07

The following costs can probably not be reimbursed during the project period (see below):

- Shipment of mouse embryos from Monterotondo, Italy to Cape Town, South Africa: 2433,23 EUR
- Shipment of dry shipper back to Monterotondo, Italy: 2085,76 EUR

Deviation from Planned Action

As mentioned above in the summary of activities, the shipment of embryos was severely delayed due to the cessation of flights to and from South Africa with the spread of the Omicron COVID-19 variant. Despite this INFRAFRONTIER will closely work with CNR-IBBC and UCT-RAF, beyond the end of the RI-VIS project (31 January 2022), to bring this project to completion as the outcome of this endeavour will have a wide-spread impact on the quality and reproducibility of pre-clinical research using mouse models in Africa.

Conclusion/Next steps

The RI-VIS Kick-Start Awards clearly and successfully demonstrated that wide impact can be achieved within focused and relatively short-term activities, particularly if they can build on already existing links between European and international research infrastructures. Pilot grants such as these should be considered a useful instrument to explore international collaborations and pave the way for larger scale projects or joint grants.

Among the impacts reported were:

- Improved international visibility of European RI services
- Identified potential funding opportunities for international collaborations
- Established material transfer agreements between European and international RIs
- Improved communication channels between European and international RIs
- Improved interoperability of operational processes of European and international RIs

In addition, all Kick-Start awardees reported that they will continue the activities targeted in their projects also after the lifetime of RI-VIS, hence the Kick-Start Awards were able to live up to their name.

Appendices

Appendix 1 – Kick-Start applications received

RI-VIS Kick-Start Awards

	EATRIS	EMBRC	EU-Openscreen	INFRAFRONTIER
Date received	30 Apr	30 Apr	30 Apr	14 May
RI-VIS Partner	EATRIS-ERIC	EMBRC-ERIC	EU-Openscreen-ERIC	INFRAFRONTIER GmbH
European Partners		EMBRC-IT EMBRC-PT		CNR-IBBC (INFRAFRONTIER-IT)
Proposal Title	Increasing EATRIS international visibility and improving usage in Australia, Brazil, Canada, Japan, UK and USA	Bioprospecting Collaboration	Bilateral collaboration between Australia and Europe in the field of chemical biology and early drug discovery	Genetic Standardisation of Reference Mouse Strains in South Africa
International Partners	Therapeutic Innovation Australia FIOCRUZ Brasil AdMare Canada AMED Japan LifeArc UK NIH-NCATS USA	IMBM - Western Cape University South Africa	Compounds Australia at Griffith University Monash University Australia Therapeutic Innovation Australia Ltd	RAF - University of Cape Town South Africa
Project Duration	Not indicated	5 months	6 months	6 months
Direct Costs	8.000 €	10.000 €	9.800 €	9.850 €

EATRIS -TT RI-VIS kickstart award proposal

In order to support internationalisation of its activities and services, EATRIS is part of the [TranslationTogether \(TT\) initiative](#). TT is a unique collaboration of leading translational research organisations from around the world leveraging their complementary scientific and operational strengths, their shared insight of the challenges facing translation, and our collective voice to advance the science and understanding of biomedical translation.

Despite the fruitful collaboration with respect to advocacy and awareness, we also identified a couple of barriers which prevent the use of available resources and services. These barriers can be grouped to the following categories

- A. Lack of information on relevant services, especially training opportunities
- B. Lack of networking opportunities for the involved researchers
- C. Lack of information on funding that could support usage of resources, services and as well as collaborative projects across continents

EATRIS submits this proposal with the purpose of increasing its international visibility and improving usage in the countries involved in TT which are Australia, Brazil, Canada, Japan, UK and USA.

As part of the kickstart proposal we will

- A. Initiate a webpage that will serve as a one-stop shop to find relevant training services and to direct users to the institutions offering these training activities.
- B. Initiate a series of virtual workshops to offer scientists the opportunity to explore collaboration opportunities for a dedicated topic and for which resources and services will be needed.
- C. Identify dedicated funding opportunities that will support access to services and resources from Brazil, Japan, Canada, US, Australia and UK.

The following steps and actions will be performed as part of the kick-start activity

- A.
 - Collect training offers from all TT partners
 - Identify how the training offers should be displayed on the website so that users can identify matching offers easily
 - Equip the website with the required technical backend (e.g. Database for filtering)
 - Tag the training offers to maximise findability across domains and global settings using [bioschemas](#) or other appropriate tools
- B.
 - Design the framework for a virtual workshop series to bring the researchers across the globe together. Enable them to identify collaboration opportunities and make them aware of existing services
 - Host 3 virtual networking events
 - Provide post-networking event support to the involved researchers in enabling them to identify and use resources and services
- C.
 - Define the criteria that funding opportunities need to meet to enable use of EATRIS services, access to the different partners and develop projects coming from networking events (amount, country coverage, scope etc.)
 - Identify suitable funding opportunities outside of Horizon Europe

Dependencies and timelines

Given the short time frame of this kickstarter activity, the streams A-C will all start in parallel in Month 1. Activities in C will be prioritised in order to be able to present suitable funding opportunities during the webinars.

Expected Impact

The kickstart proposal will enable EATRIS to improve its usage of services by international researchers. EATRIS will be visible for international researchers which will be able to network with their European counterparts, identify suitable services and how to access funding for international access.

Breakdown of costs

AMOUNT	COST CATEGORY	ACTIVITY
1,300€	Other direct costs	Database plugin for TranslationTogether website
2,700€	Other direct costs	Consultancy to identify funding that enables the TT partners to access EATRIS services & resources
4,000€	Personnel costs	Staff costs at EATRIS to coordinate the activities and implement the activities described above
2,000€	Indirect costs	
10,000€	Total costs	

Partner description

EATRIS

is the European infrastructure for translational medicine. It facilitates de-risking and adding value to drug, vaccine or diagnostic development programme. It provides fast, tailored access to cutting-edge enabling technologies in translational research. Via its central hub, it provides access to clinical expertise and high-end facilities that are available within the 100+ top-tier academic centres across Europe.

Role of EATRIS

EATRIS will coordinate the collection of training offers and the development of website specifications for the display of training services. It will design and host a minimum of 3 workshops, will define criteria for funding opportunities and identify suitable consultancies (obtaining a minimum of 3 quotes).

Translation Together (TT) partners

Translation Together is a unique collaboration of leading translational research organisations from around the world leveraging our complementary scientific and operational strengths, our shared insight of the challenges facing translation, and our collective voice to advance the science and understanding of biomedical translation. It includes partners from Australia ([Therapeutic Innovation Australia](#)), Brazil ([FIOCRUZ](#)), Canada ([AdMare](#)), Japan (Japan Agency for Research and Development ([AMED](#))), UK ([LifeArc](#)) and USA (NIH-[NCATS](#)).

Role of TT (not funded via this proposal)

The TT partners will contribute to the identification of training offers and website database specifications. They will support the design phase of the webinar and make sure that their researchers contribute to the webinars. In addition, they will help to refine the funding specifications of their geographical area.

Bioprospecting Collaboration

EMBRC – ERIC & Institute for Microbial Biotechnology and Metagenomics (IMBM), South Africa

Introduction & Rationale

Marine biodiversity is recognized as a source of particular interest for identifying novel compounds, bioactive substances, medical treatments, and biotechnologies. EMBRC has as one of its priorities the supply and access to European marine biodiversity and through a dispersed platform of infrastructures and scientific expertise gives all European scientists a gateway to unlock their value. Consequently, bioprospecting is a strategically important activity for EMBRC, tying into the blue bioeconomy strategy and Europe's Green Deal, as well as to its operators.

The uniqueness of EMBRC does not come from the instrumentation and technical capacities in themselves. It is quite clear that across science the use of equipment and methods is common. The uniqueness of the pipelines in EMBRC is the organisms that are being studied (isolated from the environment or existing as an isolate in a collection) in the countries and institutions that are affiliated to EMBRC and the custom designed and built platforms and pipelines to investigate these rich resources.

The Institute for Microbial Biotechnology and Metagenomics (IMBM) (<http://imbm.co.za/>) was established in 2007 and is based within the Department of Biotechnology at the University of the Western Cape (UWC), Bellville, South Africa. The Institute is recognised as one of the leading research units at UWC and considered a global competitor in microbial biotechnology and metagenomics. IMBM holds extensive biological resources, including 3900 bacterial isolates from South African marine, medicinal fynbos and other indigenous environments. The genomes from these isolates or metagenomes are largely unexplored, and therefore harbour great potential for the discovery of novel, high-value natural compounds for product development.

The Institute's Research and Innovation (R&I) programme focuses on the use of (meta)genomics for the development of technologies to produce novel, high-value natural products for the pharmaceutical, cosmeceutical, food & beverage and agricultural industries, as well as products for industrial applications. The vision of the IMBM is to establish itself as a preferred technology developer in the area of natural and novel leads for these industries. The R&I programme is aligned with national and global challenges and aims to deliver tangible outputs and to impact on a number of international and national priorities. The intended R&D outcomes closely fit a number of national and global socio-economic priorities.

Dr Anita Burger, the IMBM Research and Innovation Manager contacted Dr Nicolas Pade, Executive Director of EMBRC-ERIC, in October 2020 after reading about the EMBRIC project and the services and facilities of the EMBRC research infrastructure which was established to support research and innovation from marine biological resources. Her enquiry was on the availability of expertise and infrastructure in the EMBRC for the isolation and characterisation of bioactive(s) of interest to the IMBM R&I programme. The IMBM would greatly benefit from access to screening platforms, particularly antifungal and antibacterial activity, which would speed up its biodiscovery programme.

The proposed project will be on the isolation and characterisation of specific bioactives from a number of priority samples from IMBM. This is a very important opportunity for EMBRC to valorise its bioprospecting capabilities, which is one of the RIs strategic priorities. It is also an opportunity to establish a relationship between the IMBM (South Africa) and the EMBRC. For IMBM, this project offers an opportunity to explore and test the EMBRC capabilities to assess if it meets their needs in bioprospecting. If successful as a demonstrator, this project will build the foundation for a continuing collaboration. With reference to South Africa's unique biodiversity and IMBM's microbial collections and expertise, the proposed project can position the participants for future collaboration in larger inter-continental (early) product development opportunities. The proposed project may also provide an opportunity to provide training and skills development to both the IMBM and the EMBRC.

South Africa is a strategically important region for international collaboration for EMBRC, due to the highly interesting ecosystem created by the meeting of the Benguela and Agulhas currents, and generally the country's unique biodiversity. EMBRC is already in discussions with the South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON) around genomic observation. The collaboration with IMBM would also offer the opportunity to link ocean biodiversity observation and bioprospecting in South Africa in a similar manner as what is planned in EMBRC.

Due to the strict Access and Beneficiary Sharing regulations in South Africa, IMBM is facilitating the access to South African biodiversity and ensuring that all benefits are generated nationally. EMBRC is acting as a service provider providing an important missing link in the IMBM's bioprospecting pipeline. Combined, EMBRC and IMBM will be able to boost South African bioprospecting capabilities, in the first instance, and the experience gained will be deployed to generally improve bioprospecting capabilities in Europe and Africa.

Project Plan

Preamble – steps already taken to facilitate the collaboration:

The necessary authorization is in place for the shipping to Europe of IMBM extracts from indigenous microorganisms. Since only inactive extracts and no live organisms, cultures or organism biomass will be shipped the assessed biosecurity risks is negligible to nil. Therefore, no delays or failures to execute the project due to issues of material transfer are anticipated.

Objective of the study:

- a) Purification and structural characterisation of a lichenysin from a crude extract provided by the IMBM at EMBRC-Portugal (PT), Centro de Ciências do Mar (CCMAR). The predicted SMILES structure according to which the compound can be purified, will be provided by the IMBM;
- b) Bioactivity screening of the purified lichenysin or relatively pure fractions at EMBRC-Italy (IT), Stazione Zoologica Anton Dornh;
- c) Bioactivity screening of one (or if time allows it, two) purified lantipeptides provided by the IMBM at EMBRC-IT.

Operational procedure:

A multi-node approach will be taken to gain access to the unique chemistry (EMBRC-PT) and screening (EMBRC-IT) expertise within EMBRC. This approach will strengthen the service offer of EMBRC and will also allow testing of platform manager communication and permit refinement of interoperability of geographically distant nodes.

- **May 2021:** EMBRC and IMBM project team meetings for calibration of methods and volumes/amounts of the crude extract and purified compounds to be provided by the IMBM, methods for extract and compound stabilization, associated shipping requirements, permits and transport logistics;
- **June - July 2021:** IMBM preparation and shipping of crude extract to EMBRC-PT for the purification and structural characterisation of lichenysin;
- **July – August 2021:** IMBM preparation and shipping of the purified lantipeptide(s) to EMBRC for screening by one of the EMBRC screening platforms for natural marine compound bioactivity detection (EMBRC-IT; targetting the anti-microbial screens). Assign bioactivity(ies) to the purified lantipeptide(s);
- **July - September 2021:** EMBRC-PT to perform structural characterisation of the purified lichenysin;
- **August – September 2021:** EMBRC-PT provides the purified lichenysin or relatively pure fractions of lichenysin for bioactivity screening by EMBRC-IT; targetting the anti-microbial screens. Assign bioactivity(ies) to the purified lichenysin or relatively pure fractions;
- **September 2021:** Results returned to IMBM for evaluation;
- **October 2021:** follow-up meeting to discuss results, satisfaction and expertations for future collaboration. Opportunities for training and sharing of best practices will also be part of the discussions.

Partner Descriptions

European Marine Biological Resource Centre – EMBRC

The European Marine Biological Resource Centre is established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium, a legal entity created under EU law. It is a distributed research Infrastructure designed to provide access to marine biological resources and marine ecosystems to support fundamental and applied marine biology and ecology research, and promote the development of biotechnologies in the food, health and environmental sectors.

EMBRC-ERICs offers access to biological resources (wild types, model organisms, culture collections, and model organisms), ecosystems, experimental (aquaria, mesocosms, wet-and dry-laboratory space) and technological platforms (imaging, molecular biology and 'omics, telemetry, structural and chemical analysis, bioprospecting pipeline) across 9 European countries, and 45 sites. In addition to access to bioresources, equipment and platforms, EMBRC is establishing a genomic observatory for biodiversity observation and bioprospecting from marine microorganisms.

In the context of this project EMBRC is making parts of its bioprospecting pipeline and expertise available, particularly the screening for various bioactive compounds and the chemical characterization of identified targets.

The Institute for Microbial Biotechnology and Metagenomics, University of the Western Cape (UWC), South Africa - IMBM

The Institute for Microbial Biotechnology and Metagenomics (IMBM) is a leading research unit based within the Department of Biotechnology at the University of the Western Cape (UWC). The Institute is a global competitor in microbial biotechnology and metagenomics and is committed to excellence in research and in the training of future research leaders. Its research encompasses a number of disciplines including microbiology, (meta)genomics, molecular biology, enzymology and bioinformatics, and employs culture-based approaches as well as cutting edge "omics" strategies to study microbiomes, and identify novel biosynthetic gene clusters and metabolites. The Institute focuses on the research and development of novel, high-value natural products for the pharmaceutical, cosmeceutical, food & beverage and agricultural industries, as well as products for industrial processes.

The IMBM's most competitive advantages are:

- Extensive biological resources including over 3900 bacterial isolates from South African marine, medicinal fynbos and other indigenous environments. The genomes from these isolates or metagenomes are largely unexplored, and therefore harbour great potential for the discovery of novel, high-value natural compounds for product development;
- A team of 14 academic, administrative and technical staff members and about 40 post-graduate students with expertise in a number of disciplines including microbiology, (meta)genomics, molecular and structural biology, enzymology, bioinformatics and biochemistry, and employs culture-based approaches, as well as cutting edge "omics" strategies to study microbiomes, and identify novel biosynthetic gene clusters and metabolites from bacterial isolate collections
- Highly experienced in sequencing and cutting edge "omics" technologies to gain insight into the novelty of a product on genomic level i.e. prior to expression, purification and characterisation, to identify and study secondary metabolite pathways, and to manipulate the expression of compounds of interest via bacterial-based production processes.

In the context of this project IMBM is providing the biological material for screening, particularly the extracts from marine sponge bacteria from South Africa of particular interest as targets of anti-microbial and anti-cancer.

Predicted Costs

Bioactivity Screening of Lantipeptide(s) and Lichenysin

- Total expected cost €5000

Chemical Analysis:

- Lichenysin crude extract prepared for purification and chemical characterisation.
- Fractionation and purification by HPLC of the extract. Analysis of the fractions and structural characterisation of lichenysin using mass spectrometry and NMR. Shipping of the purified lichenysin(s) to EMBRC-IT for bioactivity screening.
- Total expected cost: €5000

RI-VIS Kick-Start Awards – Call for proposals to increase visibility and improve usage of research infrastructures

Pilot project to establish a bilateral collaboration between Australia and Europe in the field of chemical biology and early drug discovery

The major approach to identifying novel chemical probes (which are useful tools to study basic biological processes) and novel lead compounds (which can be further progressed into drug candidates and ultimately medicines) is the screening of large, diverse compound collections. The quality of the compound collection is of utmost importance. Indeed, pharmaceutical companies have made significant investments in the past decades to improve their own compound collections. Most academic compound collections mainly comprise compounds which are commercially available, but proprietary compounds synthesized by academic chemists as well as natural products represent a rich, untapped source for novel chemical diversity.

The storage, curation and distribution as well as the screening of these collections require a dedicated infrastructure. In Europe and Australia, EU-OPENSSCREEN and Griffith University's Compounds Australia, located at the Griffith Institute for Drug Discovery, have been established to provide access to such critical infrastructure and expertise. Together with Therapeutic Innovation Australia (TIA), a not-for-profit research infrastructure organization that supports Australian Government Initiatives, the three parties signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) in 2015.

Here we propose a 6-month pilot project between several Australian (Griffith University, Therapeutic Innovation Australia and Monash University) and European partners (EU-OPENSSCREEN) to **establish a bilateral collaboration based on the reciprocal exchange of compounds and bioactivity data.**

The project partners will explore the possibility to:

- Make synthetic and purified natural product compounds from Australia available to EU-OPENSSCREEN; and to
- Make the EU-OPENSSCREEN fragment library available to Compounds Australia.

Required steps and actions:

Before all parties sign a legally binding cooperation agreement and initiate the physical exchange of compounds, a number of topics will need to be discussed in more detail and ultimately agreed upon. Relevant topics include IPR, data exchange (e.g. structural data of compounds, screening/bioactivity data) and deposition in EU-OPENSSCREEN's open-access European Chemical Biology Database (ECBD, <http://www.ecbd.eu/>), standardization (data, operation), selection of compounds, access to compounds, dissemination and raising awareness among scientific community, and mutual exchange of experiences.

Project plan:

Based on previous discussions, the project partners propose to address these topics separately for three different use cases: synthetic compounds, natural compounds and fragments, with different Australian partners involved.

Case study A – Synthetic compounds: Prof. Jonathan Baell at Monash University in Melbourne is a Medicinal Chemist with a research interest in screening libraries and

chemoinformatics, hit-to-lead and lead optimization medicinal chemistry, drug discovery and pre-clinical development of new drug candidates. He has several hundred pure, well characterized synthetic compounds available in his laboratory, which are curated by Compounds Australia in Brisbane and represent attractive candidates for possible compound submissions to EU-OPENSSCREEN.

Case study B – Natural products: Griffith Institute of Drug Discovery (GRIDD) leads the way in Natural Product research as evident by the contributions from leading Natural Product chemists Prof. Ron Quinn, Assoc Prof Rohan Davis and Assoc Prof Yun Feng. GRIDD is also home to NatureBank, the world's first integrated drug discovery platform encompassing 18,000 natural product extracts and 90,000 natural product fractions from plants and marine invertebrates. The focus of this use case will be on the GRIDD Natural Product Derived Compounds Set; a set of >500 pure natural products or derivatives, which represents a valuable set of candidate molecules for European biologists interested in the discovery of new anti-infective and anti-cancer compounds.

As a research infrastructure, EU-OPENSSCREEN offers chemists to make their compounds available, in a regulated and transparent framework, to a wider European community of biologists, who screen these compounds in suitable bioassays. By doing so, chemists can expose their compounds to a broad range of different biological targets to screen for unknown bioactivities of their compounds, which would otherwise not be feasible in 1:1-collaborations. Once a compound has been identified as an active 'hit' compound, a research collaboration between the Australian chemist (who submitted the compound) and European biologist (who developed the bioassay) can be initiated.

For the compound submission, EU-OPENSSCREEN defined general requirements, e.g. screening data deposition after an optional embargo period of up to three years (to safeguard IPR of researchers) into the ECBD; disclosure of compound structures; purity of compounds (>90%); minimum amount of material. Together with Prof. Baell and Griffith University researchers, respectively, we will discuss whether these requirements are acceptable for Australian chemists and applicable to synthetic and natural products, and identify areas for which amendments are needed. A draft agreement (MTA) for compound submissions is available to swiftly initiate these discussions along a pre-defined set of guidelines. After agreeing on these terms, sets of compounds will be selected and physical samples prepared for compound submissions, with the support of Compounds Australia. A process to deposit the structural and bioactivity data into the ECBD is already in place. Once integrated into EU-OPENSSCREEN'S screening collection, the submitted compounds will be carefully characterized and annotated for basic physico-chemical (e.g. solubility, light absorbance, autofluorescence) and biological properties (e.g. cytotoxicity, antibiotic resistance) by testing them in a standard panel of assays, and can then be made available to European biologists.

After the successful implementation of this pilot project, we will reach out to other Australian chemists who may be interested in submitting synthetic or natural product compounds, through Compounds Australia.

Case study C – Fragments: EU-OPENSSCREEN recently acquired a new fragment library, with 968 fragments and 88 'minifrag's, derived from the fragment space of the EU-OPENSSCREEN screening library with 100,000 compounds. This fragment library is made available for fragment-based drug discovery projects at selected structural biology laboratories. The identified fragments will then be progressed further by EU-OPENSSCREEN chemistry sites. In Australia, the Monash Fragment Platform provides academic and commercial researchers with access to fragment-based drug discovery (FBDD) technologies for their therapeutic targets, and uses its own high-quality, in-house fragment library which is

curated by Compounds Australia. Compounds Australia also maintains a small fragment library made available through the University of Adelaide.

During this 6-month pilot project, we will share structural information of the available libraries to analyze the similarity of both collections. We will consider exchanging fragments if all sides agree that both collections are complementary to each other. A template agreement on the use of the EU-OPENSSCREEN fragment library is already available.

Gantt-Chart

	Month					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Case Study A+B						
Kick-off case studies	█					
Discussion on legal agreement		█	█	█		
Selection of compounds				█		
Shipment of compounds					█	
Data sharing (chemical structures)					█	
Integration of submitted compounds in EU-OPENSSCREEN's compound collection						█
Compounds ready for testing						█
Case Study C						
Kick-off case study	█					
Data sharing on fragment libraries		█				
Analysis of structural data			█	█		
Discussion on legal agreement		█	█	█		
Shipment of compounds					█	
Receipt, reformatting etc. of samples						█
Compounds ready for testing						█

Expected impact:

Based on three case studies, a framework process for the exchange of compounds (synthetic compounds, natural product compounds, and fragments) and data will be defined and tested. This model will then be extended to other chemists who may be interested in sharing their compounds. In the long-term, EU-OPENSSCREEN's compound submission model functions as an 'incubator', as it is expected to initiate multiple research collaborations between Australian chemists and European biologists. These collaborations are of mutual interest as chemists uncover bioactivities of their compounds and provide compound analogues during the hit-to-lead optimization, while biologists have access to novel chemical diversity.

After the implementation of these initial case studies, the European and Australian RIs will raise awareness among the European and Australian scientific communities about the opportunities of accessing these RIs (e.g. compound submissions by Australian chemists; testing of the Australian compounds and natural products by European biologists).

Compounds Australia and EU-OPENSSCREEN (incl. some of our local partner sites) operate highly specialized compound management facilities, and will initiate a mutual exchange of experience. There is also an interest in a similar exchange of experience between NatureBank and EU-OPENSSCREEN in the field of marine bioprospecting, as EU-OPENSSCREEN and two

partner sites are members of the new Horizon 2020-funded marine bioprospecting project 'MARBLES'.

Furthermore, all project partners will explore funding sources for joint projects (for example, Prof. Jonathan Baell and EU-OPENSSCREEN submitted a joint Horizon 2020-proposal last year). Therapeutic Innovation Australia has developed a voucher-style researcher access scheme (Pipeline Accelerator). Researchers from academia and industry can apply for a voucher of up to \$50,000 AUD to reduce the cost of accessing one or more facilities associated with TIA, including core facilities and HTS centres.

Breakdown of costs:

The total requested amount for this pilot project is 9,800€.

- 1,500€ consumable cost for the storage and reformatting of compounds, including racks, tips, plates, organic solvents.
- 1,900€ for the shipment of compounds
- 800€ consumable cost for the quality control of submitted compounds, including tips, and plates
- 5,600€ personnel cost

Project partners:

EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC (www.eu-openscreen.eu) is the European Research Infrastructure for Chemical Biology and brings together chemical biology networks and partner institutions for high-throughput screening and medicinal chemistry across eight European countries. The international not-for-profit EU-OPENSSCREEN ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) was founded in April 2018, with Germany as the host country, and is jointly funded by eight countries on a long-term basis. EU-OPENSSCREEN operates the open-access European Chemical Biology Database (ECBD) and a central compound management facility which manages, curates and distributes EU-OPENSSCREEN's compound collections, incl. a diversity collection of ca. 100,000 compounds, a collection with ca. 2,500 known bioactives, a fragment library and a growing collection of compounds that are being submitted by chemists. Contact person: **Bahne Stechmann**

Compounds Australia at Griffith University: GRIDD's Compounds Australia is Australia's only dedicated compound management facility and securely stores and curates sample libraries submitted by Australian-based chemists. Compounds Australia provides access to critical infrastructure and expertise to ensure flexible, efficient, reproducible and cost-effective compound management, supporting biological characterisation of compounds throughout the drug discovery pipeline. It manages a national 'Open' compound collection (information attached), and numerous 'Closed' or proprietary compound collections and provides these sample collections to academic, not-for-profit and industry researchers. The guiding principles of Compounds Australia are to enable new collaborations between chemists and biologists and to add value to the already excellent synthetic, organic and natural product chemistry in the Australasian region. Contact person: **Moana Simpson, Wilma James**

Griffith University: Natural products have been the single most productive source of leads for the development of drugs. In the area of cancer, over the time frame from 1981 to date, 64.9% of approved drugs and drug candidates are of natural origin. The Griffith Institute for Drug Discovery (GRIDD) at Griffith University has a long history and formidable reputation in natural product drug discovery research. Led by A/Prof Yun Feng, GRIDD chemists are leveraging this expertise through the establishment of a GRIDD Natural Product Derived

Compounds Set comprising 500 pure compounds. This is a unique compound collection in that compounds: (i) are pure natural products from rich Australian Flora and Fauna; (ii) possess diverse structural features that cover a vast chemical space and; (iii) have drug like physicochemical properties that comply with Lipinski's rules. The GRIDD Pure Natural Product Compounds Set are deposited at Compounds Australia, part of the NCRIS-funded Therapeutic Innovation Australia network. The compound set is to provide to academic, not-for-profit and industry researchers, enabling new collaborations and value adding to other publicly accessible compounds in the Compounds Australia collection. Contact person: **Assoc Professor Yun Feng**

Monash University: The Australian Translational Medicinal Chemistry Facility (ATMCF) is hosted by the Monash Institute of Pharmaceutical Science, and with Director Professor Jonathan Baell, embodies considerable experience in recognition of pan-assay interference compounds (PAINS), implementing best design of quality HTS libraries and recognition of quality screening compounds, best hit triage practices and planning of efficient SAR strategies. The ATMCF has its own compound registration system and storage of stock for all proprietary compounds, a chemoinformatics suite and all the equipment required for full QC of samples of interest. Contact person: **Professor Jonathan Baell**

Therapeutic Innovation Australia Ltd (TIA): Therapeutic Innovation Australia (TIA) is the lead agent for the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy "Therapeutic Innovation Australia" project funded by the Australian Department of Education, Skills and Employment. To enhance the progression of early-stage discoveries through to preclinical development, TIA has formed a Small Molecules Capability which is an integrated capability network of five National Research Infrastructure (NRI) across Australia, including Compounds Australia and ATMCF. This group of NRI caters to the needs of researchers and SMEs in search of expertise to progress small molecules, from accessing a unique compound and hit identification at one end of the drug discovery pipeline to a drug candidate being progressed into an IND- or CTN-enabling toxicology program at the other. To further support researchers and SMEs, TIA has established Pipeline Accelerator, a voucher-based access scheme. This scheme is intended to reduce the cost of access to capability within TIA Consortium, including a network of high throughput screening centres. Contact person: **Stuart Newman, MJ Chua**

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Proposal title: Genetic Standardisation of Reference Mouse Strains in South Africa

Contact: Dr. Asrar Ali Khan (asrar.khan@infrafrontier.eu)

Partner Descriptions

INFRAFRONTIER (RI-VIS partner) is the European Research Infrastructure for the development, phenotyping, archiving and distribution of mammalian models. INFRAFRONTIER provides access to first-class resources and services for biomedical research that includes access to physical procedures and resources (model development, archiving and distribution), analytical platforms (systemic and specialized phenotyping), knowledge (training schools) and scientific data (genetic and phenotypic data). Therefore, contributing to improved understanding of gene functions from mouse to human. The INFRAFRONTIER network of 29 partners is engaged in several EC funded projects such as INFRAFRONTIER2020, EOSC-Life, EJP-RD as well as in the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC)

International partners

- **UCT-RAF:** The University of Cape Town (UCT) Research Animal Facility (RAF) is the leading academic research animal facility in South Africa and in Africa. Situated in the top-ranked University and Health Sciences faculty on the African continent, the UCT-RAF supports the work of over 80 African research groups (academic & industry), 220 active researchers, and international collaborations with over 65 institutions. The UCT-RAF provides unique and high-quality research infrastructure, including the only rodent reproduction biotechnology laboratory in Africa (with the capability to produce, distribute, archive and rederive Specified Pathogen-Free rodents); biosafety level 1, 2 and 3 laboratories (including COVID-19 therapeutics and vaccines); the breeding of SPF rodents with distribution to animal research institutions across South Africa; and presenting the only FELASA-accredited training course in Africa (one of only two accredited courses outside Europe). The UCT-RAF complies with the required national standards and legislation for animal research and as such acts as an established reference centre and gateway to Africa for high quality-standards in laboratory animal science and ethics on the African continent.
- **CNR-IBBC:** The National Research Council (CNR), with more than 8000 employees and over 90 Institutes, is the largest multidisciplinary public research and technological development institution in Italy. The Institute of Biochemistry and Cell Biology (IBBC) is part of the "Adriano Buzzati-Traverso" International Scientific Campus, in Monterotondo (Rome) and the Italian partner of INFRAFRONTIER ESFRI Landmark Research Infrastructure (www.esfri.eu). CNR-IBBC coordinates the national node of the INFRAFRONTIER-European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA) and Mouse Clinic

Infrastructures (International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium, IMPC) for generation, primary and specialized phenotyping analysis, cryopreservation and distribution of mutant mouse strains as models of human pathologies. The Infrafrontier-EMMA group at CNR-IBBC Monterotondo actively contributes to IMPC, EOSC-Life and PATHBIO. With an estimated total capacity of more than 50,000 live animals, over 100,000 frozen germplasm stock and over 1000 produced and/or archived model strains, the repository is the largest nationally and the only archive with in-house production, processing and quality control of banked strains.

Project Description

Biomedical research in South Africa and Africa depends to a large extent on the use of wild type and genetically-altered rodents. However, the maintenance of the high genetic quality of rodent colonies in many (South) African institutions has been impeded by the large physical distance between the institutions and the sole reliance on international commercial suppliers of rodent lines. This translates to a prohibitively high cost for the international transport of animals, preventing the import of founder genetics to revive the genetic quality of African lines. The result is significant genetic drift over multiple decades, with largely uncontrolled and deteriorating genetic quality of research rodents in many South African and African institutions.

The UCT-RAF is uniquely positioned to assist in addressing this challenge, by importing and archiving cryopreserved rodent embryos of known genetic quality, rederiving the animals in South Africa, and distributing the strains to South African and potentially other African institutions. Other prominent research institutes like the South African PreClinical Drug Development Platform (PCDDP) have requested UCT-RAF to quality-control wild type strains, as no other rodent embryology laboratories have the required capabilities, and it is cost-prohibitive to establish new facilities. The UCT-RAF is an active member of the South African Association for Laboratory Animal Science (SAALAS) and the Pan-African Network for Laboratory Animal Science and Ethics (PAN-LASE), with the distribution of rederived animals being enabled via these networks. In this way, the project will have a wide-spread impact to many different institutions and users, both nationally and across the African sub-continent.

It is thus proposed to import cryopreserved embryos for the most commonly used wild type lines to the UCT-RAF for rederivation. Rederived lines will initially be subjected to genetic QC testing at the UCT-RAF, prior to distribution of animals to other institutions. To ensure high impact and sustainability, sufficient numbers of embryos will be supplied in order to enable three (3) sequential cycles of rederivation every 3.5 to 5 years or after ten generations for a period of 10-15 years. The embryos will be provided by CNR-IBBC Monterotondo, the Italian INFRAFRONTIER-EMMA node.

In short, given the UCT-RAF's rodent reproduction biotechnology laboratory (since 2013), and experienced embryo technologist (trained by Jackson laboratories and INFRAFRONTIER-

EMMA group at CNR-IBBC Monterotondo), this project can significantly improve the quality and reproducibility of biomedical research involving mouse models across the sub-continent.

Project Plan

Estimated Costs

All costs will be invoiced to INFRAFRONTIER GmbH (RI-VIS partner)

Provision of cryopreserved embryos for 6 wild type lines: 4000 €

This includes quality controls founder stocks and health monitoring of founder stocks

Transportation of frozen germplasm (Italy to South Africa): 2750 €

World Courier transport of cryo materials from Italy to South Africa, including return of the dry shipper

Rederivation at UCT-RAF: Operational costs are not included in this funding application

Genetic QC testing of wild type lines (384 SNP panel):

- Transport of genetic samples from UCT to Charles River: ZAR 25000 = 1500 €
- Genetic QC (Charles River): GBP 230 per strain x 6 lines = GBP 1380 = 1600 €